

Theoretical Equations for the Study of Entropy of Emotions and Enhancing Performance of Artificial Intelligence

Mark Christopher Arokiaraj, MD DM,
Cardiology, Pondicherry Institute of Medical Sciences, India, 605001.
christomark@gmail.com

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Imaginary angles entropy evaluation

In[7]:=

```
graph[{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2}{tanx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*√
= {x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}]
```

Eq-1

In[5]:=

```
graph[{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2}{tanx+itanx}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*√
= {x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}]
```

Eq-2

In[6]:=

```
graph[{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2}{tanx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*√
{x+ix^2}{sinx+isinx}] Eq-3
```


In[8]:=

```
graph[{x+ix^2}{sinx+isinx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2}{sinx+isinx}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*√
{x+ix^2}{sinx+isinx}] Eq-4
```


In[1]:=

```
graph[{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^e^x^2-{{tanx+isinx}}-{x^1/3+ix^2}*√
{x+ix^2}{sinx+itanx}]^2 Eq-5
```


In[9]:=

graph[[{x+ix²}{sinx+itanx}+{e^x+i^ex²}]²-{tanx+isinx}-{x^{1/3}+ix²}*√ Eq-6
{x+ix²}{sinx+itanx}]

In[10]:=

graph[[{x+ix³}sinx+{e^x+ie^{x³}}tanx]²-{x^{1/3}+ix³}*√{x+ix³}sinx] Eq-7

Out[10]=

In[11]:=

graph[[{x+ix³}sinx+{e^x+ie^{x³}}tanx]-[{x^{1/3}+ix³}*√{x+ix³}sinx]²] Eq-8

Out[11]=

In[12]:=

graph[[{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+ie^x}tanx]-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx]^2] Eq-9

Out[12]=

In[13]:=

graph[[{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+ie^x}tanx]^2-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx] Eq-10

Out[13]=

In[1]:=

graph[[{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+ie^x}tanx]^2-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx]^1/3] Eq-11

Out[1]=

In[2]:=

graph[[{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+ie^x}tanx]^1/3-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx]^2 Eq-12

In[3]:=

[[{x+ix}sinx+{e^x+ie^x}tanx]-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx] Eq-13

$$\text{Out[3]= } (1+i)x \sin[x] - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x \sin[x] + (1+i)e^x \tan[x]}$$

$$\text{In[4]= } \partial_x \left((1+i)x \sin[x] - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x \sin[x] + (1+i)e^x \tan[x]} \right)$$

$$\text{Out[4]= } (1+i)x \cos[x] - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x \cos[x] + (1+i)e^x \sec[x]^2} + (1+i) \sin[x] - \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)(x^{1/3} + ix) \sin[x]}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} - \left(i + \frac{1}{3x^{2/3}}\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x \sin[x] + (1+i)e^x \tan[x]}$$

$$\text{In[5]:=} \int \left((1+i)x \cos[x] - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \cos[x] + (1+i)e^x \sec[x]^2 + (1+i) \sin[x] - \frac{\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i}{2}\right)(x^{1/3} + ix) \sin[x]}{\sqrt{(1+i)x}} - \left(i + \frac{1}{3x^{2/3}}\right) \sqrt{(1+i)x} \sin[x] + (1+i)e^x \tan[x] \right) dx$$

$$\text{Out[5]=} \frac{1}{240} \left(\frac{90 \sqrt{\pi} x \sqrt{(1+i)x} \operatorname{Erf}[\sqrt{-ix}]}{(-ix)^{3/2}} + (1+3i) \left((48-24i) + (24+48i)e^{-ix} x - (24+48i)e^{ix} x - \frac{(27+9i)\sqrt{\pi} \sqrt{(1+i)x}}{\sqrt{-ix}} - (36+12i)e^{-ix} x^{1/3} \sqrt{(1+i)x} + (12-36i)e^{-ix} x \sqrt{(1+i)x} + (12+24i)e^{ix} ((1+i)x)^{3/2} - \frac{(18-9i)\sqrt{2\pi} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \operatorname{Erf}\left[\frac{(1+i)\sqrt{x}}{\sqrt{2}}\right]}{\sqrt{x}} - \frac{(18-9i)\sqrt{2\pi} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \operatorname{Erfi}\left[\frac{(1+i)\sqrt{x}}{\sqrt{2}}\right]}{\sqrt{x}} - (18-9i)\sqrt{(-2-2i)\pi} \operatorname{Erfi}\left[\sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} - \frac{i}{2}} \sqrt{(1+i)x}\right] + \frac{(30+10i)(-ix)^{7/6} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \operatorname{Gamma}\left[\frac{5}{6}, -ix\right]}{x^{5/3}} + \frac{(36+12i)x^{1/3} \sqrt{(1+i)x} \operatorname{Gamma}\left[\frac{11}{6}, -ix\right]}{(-ix)^{5/6}} + (48+96i)e^x \operatorname{Hypergeometric2F1}\left[-\frac{i}{2}, 1, 1-\frac{i}{2}, -e^{2ix}\right] - 48e^{(1+2i)x} \operatorname{Hypergeometric2F1}\left[1, 1-\frac{i}{2}, 2-\frac{i}{2}, -e^{2ix}\right] - 192ie^{(1+2i)x} \operatorname{Hypergeometric2F1}\left[1-\frac{i}{2}, 2, 2-\frac{i}{2}, -e^{2ix}\right] \right) \right)$$

In[1]:=

$$\text{Eq-14} \quad \boxed{[\{x \sin x + ix\} + \{e^x + 2 \tan x + i e^x\} - \{x^{1/3} \sin x + ix\} \cdot \sqrt{x^2 + ix}]}$$

$$\text{Out[1]=} i e^x + ix + x \sin[x] - \sqrt{ix + x^2} (ix + x^{1/3} \sin[x]) + e^{x^2} \tan[x]$$

$$\text{In[2]=} \text{Simplify}[i e^x + ix + x \sin[x] - \sqrt{ix + x^2} (ix + x^{1/3} \sin[x]) + e^{x^2} \tan[x]]$$

$$\text{Out[2]=} i e^x + ix + x \sin[x] - \sqrt{x(i+x)} (ix + x^{1/3} \sin[x]) + e^{x^2} \tan[x]$$

$$\text{In[3]:= } \partial_x \left(i e^x + i x + x \sin[x] - \sqrt{x(i+x)} (i x + x^{1/3} \sin[x]) + e^{x^2} \tan[x] \right)$$

$$\text{Out[3]= } i + \frac{1}{2} i i e^x e^x \pi + x \cos[x] + e^{x^2} \sec[x]^2 + \sin[x] -$$

$$\sqrt{x(i+x)} \left(i + x^{1/3} \cos[x] + \frac{\sin[x]}{3 x^{2/3}} \right) - \frac{(i+2x)(i x + x^{1/3} \sin[x])}{2 \sqrt{x(i+x)}} + 2 e^{x^2} x \tan[x]$$

$$\text{In[4]:= } \text{TrigReduce} \left[i + \frac{1}{2} i i e^x e^x \pi + x \cos[x] + e^{x^2} \sec[x]^2 + \sin[x] - \right.$$

$$\left. \sqrt{x(i+x)} \left(i + x^{1/3} \cos[x] + \frac{\sin[x]}{3 x^{2/3}} \right) - \frac{(i+2x)(i x + x^{1/3} \sin[x])}{2 \sqrt{x(i+x)}} + 2 e^{x^2} x \tan[x] \right]$$

$$\text{Out[4]= } i + \frac{1}{2} i i e^x e^x \pi - i \sqrt{x(i+x)} + \frac{\sqrt{x(i+x)}}{2(i+x)} - \frac{i x \sqrt{x(i+x)}}{i+x} + x \cos[x] - x^{1/3} \sqrt{x(i+x)} \cos[x] +$$

$$e^{x^2} \sec[x]^2 + \sin[x] - \frac{\sqrt{x(i+x)} \sin[x]}{3 x^{2/3}} + \sec[x] (-i e^{x^2} x \cos[x] + e^{x^2} x \sin[x]) +$$

$$\sec[x] \left(i e^{x^2} x \cos[x] + e^{x^2} x \sin[x] \right) + \frac{-\frac{\sqrt{x(i+x)} \cos[x]}{4 x^{2/3}} - \frac{i \sqrt{x(i+x)} \sin[x]}{4 x^{2/3}}}{i+x} + \frac{\frac{\sqrt{x(i+x)} \cos[x]}{4 x^{2/3}} - \frac{i \sqrt{x(i+x)} \sin[x]}{4 x^{2/3}}}{i+x} +$$

$$\frac{-\frac{1}{2} i x^{1/3} \sqrt{x(i+x)} \cos[x] - \frac{1}{2} x^{1/3} \sqrt{x(i+x)} \sin[x]}{i+x} + \frac{\frac{1}{2} i x^{1/3} \sqrt{x(i+x)} \cos[x] - \frac{1}{2} x^{1/3} \sqrt{x(i+x)} \sin[x]}{i+x}$$

In[5]:=

Graph [$\{x \sin x + i x\} + \{e^x \wedge 2 \tan x + i e^x\} - \{x \wedge 1/3 \sin x + i x\} * \sqrt{\{x \wedge 2 + i x\}}$] Eq-15

In[6]:=

Graph [{"xsinx+ix} + {e^x^2tanx+i^e^x} - i{x^1/3sinx+ix}*√{x^2+ix}] Eq-16

In[7]:=

Graph [i{xsinx+ix} + {e^x^2tanx+i^e^x} - {x^1/3sinx+ix}*√{x^2+ix}] Eq-17

Graph {xsinx + ix} + {e^x^2 tanx + i^e^x} - {x^1/3 sinx + ix} * √{x^2 + ix}]

In[8]:=

[[{x+ix}sinx^2 + {e^x+ie^x}tanx^2] - [{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx^2] Eq-18

$$\text{Out[8]= } (1+i)x \sin[x]^2 - (x^{1/3} + ix) \sqrt{(1+i)x \sin[x]^2 + (1+i)e^x \tan[x]^2}$$

In[9]:=

graph[[{x+ix}sinx^2+{e^x+ie^x}tanx^2]-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx^2] Eq-19

Out[9]=

In[10]:=

graph[[{x+ix}sinx^3+{e^x+ie^x}tanx^3]-[{x^1/3+ix}*√{x+ix}sinx^3] Eq-20

Out[10]=

In[11]:=

graph[[{x+ix^2}sinx^3+{e^x+ie^x^2}tanx^3]-[{x^1/3+ix^2}*√{x+ix^2}sinx^3] Eq-21

Out[11]=

In[14]:=
$$[[\{dx/dt+idx/dt\}sinx+\{de^x/dt+ide^x/dt\}tanx]-[\{dx^{1/3}/dt+idx/dt\}*\sqrt{\{dx/dt+idx/dt\}sinx}]$$
 Eq-22
 Out[14]= 0

In[15]:=
$$[[\{dx/dt+dix/dt\}sinx+\{de^x/dt+die^x/dt\}tanx]-[\{dx^{1/3}/dt+dix/dt\}*\sqrt{\{dx/dt+dix/dt\}sinx}]$$
 Eq-23
 Out[15]= 0

In[16]:=
$$[[\{d^2x/dt^2+dix/dt\}sinx+\{de^{x^2}/dt+die^{x^2}/dt\}tanx]-[\{dx^{1/3^2}/dt^2+dix^2/dt^2\}*\sqrt{\{dx^2/dt^2+dix^2/dt^2\}sinx}]$$
 Eq-24
 Out[16]= 0

In[1]:=
$$[[\{dx/dt+dix/dt\}sinx+\{de^x/dt+die^x/dt\}]-[\{dx^{1/3}/dt+dix/dt\}*\sqrt{\{dx/dt+dix/dt\}sinx}]$$
 Eq-25
 Out[1]= 0

In[2]:=
$$\text{graph}[[\{x/t+ix/t\}sinx+\{e^x/t+ie^x/t\}tanx]-[\{x^{1/3}/t+ix/t\}*\sqrt{\{x/t+dix/t\}sinx}]$$
 Eq-26

In[3]:= Show[%2, Background → RGBColor[0.97, 0.93, 0.68]]

In[4]:=

⊞ solve[{{x/t+ix/t}sinx+{e^x/t+ie^x/t}tanx}-{{x^1/3/t+ix/t}*√{x/t+dix/t}sinx}] Eq-27

Out[4]=
$$\frac{(1+i)x \sin[x]}{t} - \left(\frac{x^{1/3}}{t} + \frac{ix}{t} \right) \sqrt{\frac{509}{t} + \frac{x}{t}} \sin[x] + \frac{(1+i)e^x \tan[x]}{t}$$

In[5]:= Simplify[
$$\frac{(1+i)x \sin[x]}{t} - \left(\frac{x^{1/3}}{t} + \frac{ix}{t} \right) \sqrt{\frac{509}{t} + \frac{x}{t}} \sin[x] + \frac{(1+i)e^x \tan[x]}{t}$$
]

Out[5]=
$$\frac{\left((1+i)e^x + \left(-x^{1/3} \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} + x \left((1+i) - i \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \right) \right) \cos[x] \right) \tan[x]}{t}$$

In[6]:= TrigReduce[
$$\frac{\left((1+i)e^x + \left(-x^{1/3} \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} + x \left((1+i) - i \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \right) \right) \cos[x] \right) \tan[x]}{t}$$
]

Out[6]=
$$\frac{\sec[x] \left((2+2i)e^x \sin[x] + (1+i)x \sin[2x] - x^{1/3} \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \sin[2x] - ix \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \sin[2x] \right)}{2t}$$

$$\text{In}[7]:= \partial_t \frac{\text{Sec}[x] \left((2 + 2i) e^x \text{Sin}[x] + (1 + i) x \text{Sin}[2x] - x^{1/3} \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \text{Sin}[2x] - i x \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \text{Sin}[2x] \right)}{2t}$$

$$\text{Out}[7]= \frac{\text{Sec}[x] \left(\frac{x^{1/3} (509+x) \text{Sin}[2x]}{2t^2 \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}}} + \frac{i x (509+x) \text{Sin}[2x]}{2t^2 \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}}} \right)}{2t}$$

$$\frac{\text{Sec}[x] \left((2 + 2i) e^x \text{Sin}[x] + (1 + i) x \text{Sin}[2x] - x^{1/3} \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \text{Sin}[2x] - i x \sqrt{\frac{509+x}{t}} \text{Sin}[2x] \right)}{2t^2}$$

In[8]:=

graph[[{x/t+ix^2/t}sinx+{e^x/t+ie^x^2/t}tanx]-[{x^1/3/t+ix^2/t}*sqrt{x/t+dix^2/t}sinx] Eq-28

- Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.\$Aborted
- Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted
- Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted
- Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted
- General: Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.\$Aborted
- Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.\$Aborted
- Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.\$Aborted
- General: Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.\$Aborted

In[1]:=

graph[[{x^2/t+ix/t}sinx+{e^x^2/t+ie^x^2/t}tanx]-[{x^1/3^2/t+ix^2/t}*sqrt{x^2/t+dix^2/t}sinx] Eq-29

- Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.\$Aborted
- Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted
- Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted
- Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted
- General: Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.\$Aborted
- Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.\$Aborted
- Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$ encountered.\$Aborted
- General: Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.\$Aborted

In[1]:=

graph[[{x^2/t+ix/t}+{e^x^2/t+ie^x^2/t}]-[{x^1/3^2/t+ix^2/t}*√{x^2/t+dix^2/t}]]

Eq-30

Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$. encountered.\$Aborted

Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted

Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted

Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$. encountered.\$Aborted

Infinity: Indeterminate expression ComplexInfinity + ComplexInfinity encountered.\$Aborted

General: Further output of Infinity::indet will be suppressed during this calculation.\$Aborted

Power: Infinite expression $\frac{1}{0}$. encountered.\$Aborted

General: Further output of Power::infy will be suppressed during this calculation.\$Aborted

In[1]:=

graph[[{x/t+ix/t}sinx^2+{e^x/t+ie^x/t}tanx^2]-[{x^1/3/t+ix/t}*√{x/t+ix/t}sinx^2]]

Eq-31

graph[[{x/t+ix^2/t}+{e^x/t+ie^x^2/t}]-[{x^1/3/t+ix^2/t}*√{x/t+ix/t}]] Eq-32

In[3]:= **Show**[%2, ImageSize → Medium]

In[4]:=

```
graph[{{x^2/t+ix/t}+{e^x^2/t+ie^x/t}]-[x^1/3^2/t+ix/t]*sqrt{x^2/t+ix/t}] Eq-33
```

